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**Pre-Clinical Toxicity Studies of Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) in Mice and
Rats**

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The present study has been conducted to assess the pre-Clinical safety and efficacy of Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaves in mice and rat model. Albino mice (Swiss) were used in graded doses of *Azadirachta indica* by oral routes. Acute toxicity of *Azadirachta indica* showed normal behaviour and no mortality up to the 14th day. Effect of *Azadirachta indica* on haematological, biochemical and histopathological parameters in sub –acute toxicity was carried out. Sub-acute toxicity of *Azadirachta indica* was found no significant changes in haematological, biochemical parameters and histopathological examinations.

Keywords: Azadirachta indica: Acute- toxicity: Sub- Acute- toxicity: Histopathology